

How can we utilize existing company data (e.g., reporting data) for Circular Economy (CE) purposes?

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1 Do the reports provide structured indicators for all the 8 strategies?

How can we use the indicators provided for GRI and CSRD on the side. Then, can the results about to use all the 8 strategies with the best weight in the reports.

2 Major Challenges in Using Internal Company Reports to Measure Circularity

Point-based rating

3 Besides sustainability reports, are there other alternatives to obtain such data from companies? Describe

Point-based rating

GRI circularity indicators

Indicator	Description
301-1	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-2	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-3	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-4	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-5	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-6	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-7	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-8	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-9	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-10	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-11	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-12	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-13	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-14	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-15	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-16	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-17	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-18	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-19	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-20	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-21	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-22	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-23	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-24	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-25	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-26	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-27	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-28	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-29	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-30	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-31	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-32	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-33	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-34	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-35	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-36	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-37	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-38	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-39	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-40	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-41	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-42	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-43	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-44	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-45	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-46	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-47	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-48	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-49	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-50	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes

CSRD circularity indicators

Indicator	Description
301-1	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-2	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-3	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-4	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-5	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-6	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-7	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-8	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-9	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
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301-30	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-31	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-32	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
301-33	Percentage of material recycled used in manufacturing processes
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CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS OF USING COMPANIES' SUSTAINABILITY REPORTS

Challenge	Limitation	Impact on data	Need for data verification
GRI is a regulatory report	Not standardized	Difficult to compare and align	Need for data verification
Self-reporting	Not standardized	Difficult to compare and align	Need for data verification
Qualitative data	Not standardized	Difficult to compare and align	Need for data verification
Availability in reporting channels	Not standardized	Difficult to compare and align	Need for data verification
Data Gaps	Not standardized	Difficult to compare and align	Need for data verification
Dynamic Changes	Not standardized	Difficult to compare and align	Need for data verification